

Classical Maximum Entropy Probabilities Versus Quantum Dynamical Probabilities

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There is a focus in classical statistical mechanics on maximizing an entropy function subject to constraints to obtain probability values. For a coin or die probabilities are given, yet one may still calculate a Shannon's entropy. In the case of a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) gas, one may obtain probabilities using energy conservation and products of probabilities and then show this is equivalent to maximizing an entropy function subject to an energy constraint. We argue that the energy conservation approach yields an energy conservation equation and a product of probabilities representing a certain total energy equated to a product of different probabilities representing the same total energy. The two equations are linked to solve for probability in terms of energy and this is formally the same as a maximization problem subject to conservation of energy. A point we make is that this approach is based on a kind of static conservation, even in the presence of a potential $V(x)$.

In quantum mechanics, we argue one has fluxes even though there is also conservation of energy. For light moving in the positive x direction which reflects and refracts (with each photon retaining its energy) there is both energy conservation and flux. The energy conservation equation in terms of flux/intensity terms is given in (1) as: $AA/c1 = BB/c1 + CC/c2$ where A, B, C refer to the incident, reflected and refracted rays. This single equation cannot solve for probabilities B, C in terms of A and there is not a separate product of probabilities equation as in the MB case. Rather quantum mechanics seems to be solved using square root fluxes as dynamical probabilities. In particular, the energy conservation equation is equivalent to two square root flux equations $A+B=C$ and $p1A - p1B = p2C$ where $E=pc$. Thus probabilities are determined through dynamics not static conservation or entropy maximization. In an earlier note we concluded that $\exp(ipx)$, a quantum free particle wavefunction, is also like a square root flux, and also acts as a dynamic probability. These ideas may be extended to a quantum bound state which we discuss in the note.

Thus the approach to finding probabilities in the classical statistical mechanics and quantum realms seem to be completely different. One uses static conservation laws in the former and square root flux continuity/dynamical probability in the latter.

Classical Statistical Mechanics - The Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas

A traditional treatment of an MB gas involves considering various static arrangements with each being given a weight of 1. For example:

$$\# \text{Arrangements} = N! / \left(\text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)! \right) \quad ((1))$$

Using Stirling's approximation for large N and $n(e_i)$: $N! = N \ln(N)$ ((2)) and taking \ln yields:

$$\ln(\# \text{Arrangements}) = N \ln(N) - \text{Sum over } i \ n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) \quad ((3))$$

The second term on the RHS is called the entropy which may then be extremized subject to the constraint of constant average energy i.e. $\sum_i e_i n(e_i)$. This yields the MB distribution: $C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

Two alternative approaches which do make use of arrangements, but are based on static energy conservation are as follows.

First one has reaction balance with two body elastic scattering. Then there exist two conditions:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((4)) \quad \text{and} \quad n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3)n(e_4) \quad ((5))$$

Taking \ln of the latter and linking to the former yields the MB probability again.

One may note that in this conservation of energy approach one really equates: e_i with $\ln(n(e_i))$. Thus one may immediately formulate the above with an extremization problem such that the constraint (after variation) yields e_i and the "entropy" $\ln(n(e_i))$ i.e.

$$\sum_i n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) + b \sum_i n(e_i) e_i \text{ is extremized} \quad ((6))$$

$$\sum_i dn(e_i) + \sum_i dn(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) + b \sum_i dn(e_i) e_i = 0$$

One equates $\ln(n(e_i))$ with e_i which is already known from the reaction balance approach.

An alternative approach is to consider the probability for a certain total amount of energy to be independent of the number of particles creating this total. In other words if a single particle has energy e_1 and probability $n(e_1)$ and two other particles have energies e_3, e_4 such that $e_3 + e_4 = e_1$, then $n(e_3)n(e_4) = n(e_1)$. This also yields the MB distribution.

The point we wish to make is that in the classical statistical mechanical MB gas, energy conservation and product AND probabilities drive the solution of the form of $n(e_i)$. This conservation approach is also linked to the maximization of arrangements or entropy, but one could actually only think in terms of energy conservation and product probabilities alone (although arrangements and entropy maximization are equivalent.) These ideas do not seem to change if one introduces a potential $V(x)$ as one has the same energy conservation considerations at each x point and a static balance of pressure to create the spatial density $\exp(-V(x)/T)$.

Quantum Mechanics

Given the static conservation of energy approach or maximization of entropy used in classical statistical mechanics, one might think a similar approach applies to quantum mechanics. We argue that this does not seem to be the case. In fact, if one considers a reflection/refraction problem which has energy conservation and probability, it is in fact square root flux

continuity/dynamical probabilities which yields probability values. They do not follow from conservation of energy and a product of probabilities rule.

To see this explicitly consider the case of light moving in the positive x direction reflecting and refracting from a medium along the y axis at x=0. A specific photon retains its energy, but there is a probability “a” to reflect and 1-a to refract. Thus like classical statistical mechanics, one has energy conservation and the notion of probabilities, but flux is introduced as well because this is a steady state situation. Such flux does not exist in the MB gas. Following (1) one may write an energy conservation equation:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \text{ where } AA=\text{incident flux, } BB \text{ reflected and } CC \text{ refracted } ((7))$$

Here AA is used to represent intensity/flux because it is strictly positive.

((7)) is a conservation of energy equation. In classical statistical mechanics, one might try to find a second equation involving a product of probabilities, but that is not the solution in the quantum mechanical case. The qm case focuses on fluxes. In fact, energy conservation is a given so there is no need to write ((7)) in terms of fluxes unless they have some relevance. We argue that ((7)) may be rewritten as two square root flux equations:

$$A+B=C \text{ and } p_1A - p_1B = p_2C \text{ with } E=p_1c_1=p_2c_2 ((8))$$

The two square root flux equations may then be used to solve for B,C in terms of A. Thus square root flux continuity (dynamic probability) is used to find probabilities in the quantum case. The above problem is for light, but a similar one may be used for particles with rest mass if one considers two regions, one with a constant potential of V1 and the other (separated by the y axis at x=0) with a constant potential V2. Energy is conserved.

We further argue that $\exp(ipx)$ for a quantum free particle with rest mass is like a square root flux/dynamical probability. Thus the above ideas should be extended to a quantum bound state.

Quantum Bound State

A quantum bound state seems to be similar to a classical statistical mechanics gas. In fact classical statistical mechanical approaches are used to consider particles jumping from different single particle levels to others for a given temperature. Here we consider only a single quantum bound state. We argue that $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ i.e. one has a superposition of square root fluxes or dynamical probabilities. Thus dynamics seems to govern this problem, not products of probabilities. For a given $V(x)$ and E (energy) a dynamical equation consistent with a constant E at all x in classical mechanics is:

$$\{\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx) \} / \{\text{sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)\} + V(x) = E_n ((9))$$

((9)) is in fact the time-independent Schrodinger equation and $-1/2m \text{ } d/dx \text{ } d/dx \text{ } W(x) / W(x)$ replaces the first term on the LHS. One may note that $E=\text{constant}$ at all x is a equivalent to a kind of minimization of information i.e. all x points are treated alike with is in keeping with the

spatially invariant nature of $\exp(ipx)$, the quantum free particle wavefunction. This property, however, already exists in classical mechanics as noted.

This immediately yields $W(x)$ and hence the set of $\{a(p)\}$ values without any product probabilities equated with single energy values or maximization of entropy. Conservation of energy appears, but in a dynamical way. One has an OR situation with the various $\exp(ipx)$'s and these values are adjusted to give the correct dynamical $KE(x)$ (kinetic energy).

If one wanted to consider a variational problem, one could do the following:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} (W+dW) + V(x) [W + dW] = E_n [W+dW] \quad ((10))$$

This, however, does not vary $a(p)$'s separately and shows that dW is proportional to W . Thus we argue that probabilities in quantum mechanics arise very differently than in classical mechanics because at the wavelength level one deals with square root flux which acts like dynamical probability. The physical picture seems to be very different. For instance in a bound state which contains $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$, if $a(p)=a(-p)$, then one has $\cos(px)$, but this is still linked to a square root flux. $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-i\hbar/dx$ and linked to spatial invariance. If one calculates $-i\hbar/dx \cos(px) / \cos(px)$ for a bound state in an infinite well one sees that average p changes starts at 0, becomes negative, reaches 0 again then becomes positive, then 0 etc. This is dynamical behaviour and differs from classical motion. Ultimately one considers energy values $pp/2m$, but the consideration of average p shows peculiarities associated with the square root flux scenario.

The Question of Entropy

Given that quantum mechanics seems to dictate the value of "probabilities" i.e. $W(x)$ or $a(p)$ (or their corresponding $a^*(p)a(p)$, $W^*(x)W(x)$) based on dynamics instead of maximizing entropy, can one still write an entropy expression? We think that one can. A die or coin have fixed probabilities, but one may still write a general Shannon's entropy expression. This is based, however, on viewing the system from outside (where there is an external time) and considering it to be in either one $a(p)$ or another state at different times. The actual result of the bound state is an interference of $\exp(ipx)$ s with no time present i.e. steady state. Thus a calculation of entropy may be only a way of trying to quantify the probability scenario between one bound state and another.

The Oscillator Ground State

The oscillator ground state yields $a(p) = C \exp(-.5 pp/\sqrt{km})$ and $W(x) = C^2 \exp(-.5 \sqrt{km}x^2)$. These have the appearance of classical statistical mechanics results for an oscillator, but the difference is that the classical oscillator has a probability of $\exp(-C^3xx/T)\exp(-C^3pp/T)$ while one uses either $a^*(p)a(p)$ to describe the qm oscillator state with no x information or $W(x)W(x)$ to describe the density profile. Thus a classical looking scenario holds for either p or x , but not both at the same time. Nevertheless, the quantum mechanical dynamical square root flux approach leads to classical-like probabilities $W(x)W(x)$

and $a(p)a(p)$ which may be used in a Shannon's entropy formula. One must remember, however, that one ultimately deals with $a(p)$ and $W(x)$ which are dynamical (linked to square root fluxes) and their values follow from this and energy considerations, not the maximization of entropy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the notion of maximizing arrangements or entropy subject to a constraint found in classical statistical mechanics is directly linked to a scenario of two equations, one being energy conservation and the other involving products of probabilities. " \ln " is taken of the latter which is then equated to the former. Thus static energy conservation and product probabilities already link $\ln(n(e_i))$ with e_i . This may formally be written as a maximization of an $-n(e_i)\ln(n(e_i))$ function subject to a constraint $b n(e_i)$.

In quantum mechanics, we argue that one deals with square root fluxes/dynamical probabilities (continuity of wavefunction, first derivative) which yield probabilities, not conservation of energy with product probabilities. Thus quantum probabilities are governed by square root flux/dynamic probability considerations. We consider the reflection/refraction problem as demonstrating this idea. Once one has solved for $W(x)$ or $a(p)$ using square root probabilities instead of maximization of entropy, one may calculate classical-like probabilities $W^*(x)W(x)$ and $a^*(p)a(p)$ and use these in a Shannon's entropy formula, just as one would use the probabilities of a die or coin. We also argue that one might be able to formulate a Shannon's entropy at the wavelength level i.e. $a(p)/p$ as we have discussed in another note, but one does not maximize this entropy subject to constraints to find the value of $a(p)$, rather $a(p)$ follows from dynamical considerations and constant E at each x point.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change